

Applicability of CRAM to the Extended Point Kinetics System

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ABSTRACT

Delayed neutrons are conventionally represented through grouped precursor parameters in point kinetics simulations. Explicit tracking of individual precursor nuclides is nevertheless possible by solving the Bateman equations. The extended point kinetics solver developed at PSI couples the point kinetics and Bateman equations under a quasi-static neutron irradiation approximation, enabling all precursor nuclides to be followed explicitly during transients. This formulation results in a system of first order differential equations whose solution requires evaluating the matrix exponential of the system matrix. The immense stiffness of this matrix makes standard numerical methods ill-suited, which motivates the use of the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM), a method that has already shown to provide accurate and fast solutions for burnup and decay systems with similar numerical properties. However, positive reactivity introduces a positive real eigenvalue into the extended point kinetics matrix, which can limit the applicability of CRAM. In this work, the extended point kinetics matrix is analysed through its graphical representation in order to infer its spectral properties. It is shown that CRAM achieves exceptionally high accuracy once the timestep is chosen sufficiently small so that the largest eigenvalue of the system spectrum falls within the high-accuracy region of the rational approximation. A procedure for selecting the timestep based on the reactivity is introduced, and the accuracy of CRAM is demonstrated on an extended point kinetics case. Finally, the superiority of CRAM over ODE15s, a standard MATLAB solver for stiff systems, is demonstrated in terms of both accuracy and computational time on a classical six-group point kinetics problem.

Keywords: CRAM, matrix exponential, extended point kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

Delayed neutron production is conventionally represented through grouped precursor parameters. In some cases, however, the explicit evolution of individual precursor nuclides or, more generally, any specific isotope during a transient is of interest. One example is the case of molten salt reactors, where precursor nuclides drift with the circulating fuel while continuous online reprocessing occurs. Motivated by this application, the extended point kinetics solver was developed [1, 2], coupling the Bateman equations with point kinetics under a quasi-static neutron irradiation approximation. This solver evolves the full nuclide vector during the transient and explicitly accounts for the contribution of each individual precursor to delayed neutron production. Although it was originally developed for molten salt reactor studies, its ability to track the time evolution of every nuclide also makes it applicable to any case where the behaviour of specific isotopes matters, such as those relevant to radiotoxicity or decay heat.

The system matrix of the extended point kinetics solver consists of the full decay matrix, augmented by an additional first row and first column representing neutron kinetics and nuclide irradiation, respectively. Because the decay constants span many orders of magnitude, the matrix is highly stiff, which degrades the accuracy of most classical numerical methods for evaluating the matrix exponential.

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Since the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) performs well for stiff burnup and decay systems [3, 4, 5, 6], this work examines its use for the extended point kinetics system, with the results naturally applying also to the classical point kinetics formulation.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the extended point kinetics solver, and Section 3 describes CRAM as the method used to evaluate the matrix exponential. Section 4 analyses the graphical structure of the extended point kinetics matrix, derives its spectral properties, and establishes the mathematical conditions under which CRAM can be applied reliably. Numerical examples in Section 5 illustrate the accuracy of CRAM for the extended point kinetics system and demonstrate its superiority over MATLAB ODE15s on the case of the classical point kinetics system, both in accuracy and in computational time.

2. EXTENDED POINT KINETICS SYSTEM

The extended point kinetics system couples the point kinetics and Bateman equations, taking the quasi-static neutron irradiation approximation. Under this approximation, the irradiation-driven change of nuclide concentration (excluding its radioactive decay term) is evaluated using the nuclide concentration from the previous timestep and the updated neutron flux. It can be expressed as:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} \Big|_{\text{irrad. } t_n} = \left(-\sigma_{ii} N_i^{n-1} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^m \sigma_{j \rightarrow i} N_j^{n-1} \right) \phi^0 P^n, \quad (1)$$

where N_i^n is the number of nuclides corresponding to isotope i at time t_n ; N_i^{n-1} corresponds to the number of nuclides of isotope i at the end of the previous timestep t_{n-1} ; σ_{ii} and $\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}$ are the microscopic cross sections; ϕ^0 is the neutron flux at the initial steady state preceding the transient; P^n denotes the neutron population at time t_n , normalized to 1 before the start of the transient. The updated flux magnitude is the product of the initial flux magnitude before the start of the transient and the neutron population at time t_n , i.e. $\phi^0 P^n$.

Thus, the extended point kinetics system is represented in the following form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} P \\ N_1 \\ \vdots \\ N_m \end{bmatrix}_n = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(\rho(t_n) - \beta_{eff})}{\Lambda} & C^* \lambda_{1n} & \cdots & C^* \lambda_{mn} \\ \left(-\sigma_{11} N_1^{n-1} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq 1}^m \sigma_{j \rightarrow 1} N_j^{n-1} \right) \phi^0 & -\lambda_1 & \cdots & \lambda_{m \rightarrow 1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \left(-\sigma_{mm} N_m^{n-1} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq m}^m \sigma_{j \rightarrow m} N_j^{n-1} \right) \phi^0 & \lambda_{1 \rightarrow m} & \cdots & -\lambda_m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P \\ N_1 \\ \vdots \\ N_m \end{bmatrix}_n, \quad (2)$$

where $\rho(t_n)$ is the reactivity at the time t_n , β_{eff} the effective delayed neutron fraction, Λ the prompt neutron generation time, and λ_i the decay constant of nuclide i ; λ_{in} is equal to $p_{ni} \lambda_i$, where p_{ni} is the probability of nuclide i emitting a delayed neutron through its decay. The constant factor C^* is obtained from the zero-reactivity condition to normalize the initial neutron population to 1, assuming equal effectivity for all delayed neutrons:

$$\frac{-\beta_{eff}}{\Lambda} + C^* \sum_i N_i^{eq} \lambda_{in} = 0 \Rightarrow C^* = \frac{\beta_{eff}}{\Lambda \sum_i N_i^{eq} \lambda_{in}}, \quad (3)$$

where N_i^{eq} denotes the equilibrium number of nuclides of precursor i prior to the transient. Further details on the matrix structure are provided in [2].

Thus, the evolving vector y consists of the neutron population $P(t)$ and the full nuclide composition vector N . The system and its solution can be expressed in the general form:

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = A(t)y \Rightarrow y_n = e^{A_n \Delta t} y_{n-1}, \quad y(0) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \text{Neq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The time dependence of the matrix A arises from its first column, which depends on the nuclide composition from the previous timestep. After each timestep, this column is updated using the new nuclide vector.

To obtain the solution, the product of the matrix exponential and the evolving vector must be evaluated. Since the extended point kinetics matrix corresponds to the decay matrix augmented with an additional first row accounting for neutron kinetics and a first column representing neutron irradiation of nuclides, it inherits the challenging numerical properties of the decay matrix. Nuclide half-lives span from about 10^{-24} seconds to billions of years, resulting in extreme stiffness of the system. Highly unstable nuclides with large decay constants substantially increase the matrix norm, which limits the applicability of most classical methods for computing the matrix exponential, such as the truncated Taylor series or the rational Padé approximation [5]. These methods rely on approximations valid only near the origin and therefore require scaling and squaring, $e^{At} = (e^{At/m})^m$, to reduce the matrix norm. However, this procedure introduces significant round-off errors which limit their accuracy. Increasing the number of terms in the Taylor series does not improve the accuracy, as round-off errors remain dominant [5, 7]. Thus, the use of CRAM is motivated by its proven accuracy in evaluating the matrix exponential for burnup and decay systems with matrix norms and stiffness comparable to those of the extended point kinetics system.

3. CRAM FOR EVALUATING MATRIX EXPONENTIAL

Several definitions of the matrix exponential exist, but the one relevant for introducing CRAM is the definition derived from the Cauchy integral formula. Since the exponential function is analytic on the entire complex plane, the exponential of a matrix M can be written as:

$$e^M = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_G e^z (zI - M)^{-1} dz, \quad (5)$$

where G is a closed contour that encloses the spectrum of M . If a rational function $r(z)$ provides an accurate approximation of the scalar exponential e^z in the region containing the matrix spectrum, then the matrix exponential can be approximated with:

$$e^M \approx \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_G r(z) (zI - M)^{-1} dz \quad (6)$$

The Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) uses the Chebyshev rational approximation, which is the best rational approximation of the exponential function on the negative real axis [5, 8]. On \mathbb{R}^- , the approximation error equioscillates around zero and, for approximation orders higher than 16, its magnitude is reduced to a level below double-precision arithmetic. However, the region of this extremely high accuracy of the approximation extends beyond \mathbb{R}^- , which makes CRAM particularly suitable for burnup systems, since the eigenvalues of the burnup matrix predominantly lie near the negative real axis [5].

Two computationally practical forms of the approximation are commonly used for burnup calculations: the Partial Fraction Decomposition (PFD) form and the Incomplete Partial Fraction Decomposition (IPF) form. The PFD form was originally proposed for burnup calculations. However, coefficients for this form were only possible to be derived up to the 16th order [3, 5]. While the 16th-order PFD is sufficiently accurate for typical burnup calculations, higher-order approximations are required for pure decay calculations with long time steps [6]. For this reason, the IPF form was introduced, which coefficient derivation is considerably less prone to round-off errors than that of the PFD form, enabling accurate higher-order approximations with precomputed coefficients up to order 48 [6]. Both forms of the approximation are summarized in Table I. By substituting the rational approximation $r(z)$ into the integral in (6) and using the identities:

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_G (zI - M)^{-1} dz = I, \quad \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_G \frac{1}{z - \theta_j} (zI - M)^{-1} dz = (M - \theta_j I)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

yields a direct expression for the matrix exponential. The resulting algorithms for evaluating the nuclide vector after a single timestep t , starting from the initial composition N_0 with the burnup/decay matrix A , are given in Table I for both forms.

Table I. PFD and IPF forms of the Chebyshev rational approximation and the associated CRAM algorithms

Form	Partial Fraction Decomposition (PFD)	Incomplete Fraction Decomposition (IPF)
Approximation of order k in the scalar form	$r_{k,k}(x) = \alpha_0 + 2\text{Re} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{k/2} \frac{\alpha_j}{x - \theta_j} \right)$	$\hat{r}_{k,k}(x) = \alpha_0 \prod_{l=1}^{k/2} \left(1 + 2\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_l}{x - \theta_l} \right\} \right)$
	α_0 - the limit of $r_{k,k}$ at infinity, α_j - the residues at the poles θ_j	α_0 - the limit of $r_{k,k}$ at infinity, $\tilde{\alpha}_l$ - the residues of $\hat{r}_{2,2}^{(l)}, \hat{r}_{k,k} = \prod_{l=1}^{k/2} \hat{r}_{2,2}^{(l)}$
Algorithm	$y = \alpha_0 N_0$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, k/2$ $y = 2\text{Re} \left(\alpha_j (At - \theta_j I)^{-1} N_0 \right) + y$ end for	$y = N_0$ for $l = 1, 2, \dots, k/2$: $y = 2\text{Re}(\alpha_l (At - \theta_l I)^{-1} y) + y$ end for $y = \alpha_0 y$

In both cases, the computation reduces to solving a sequence of linear systems:

$$(At - \theta_l I) y_l = x, \quad (8)$$

where A is the system matrix, θ_l are the poles of the rational approximation, and x is the right-hand-side vector (N_0 for the PFD form or the current iterate y for the IPF form). The final solution is obtained as a combination of the intermediate vectors y_l , weighted by the corresponding residues α_l . The coefficients of the approximation (α_l, θ_l) are precomputed constants that depend only on the form and the order of the approximation.

Finally, unlike Taylor or Padé based methods, which require scaling and squaring for matrices with a large norm and therefore suffer from the rounding errors introduced in that process, CRAM is not constrained by the magnitude of the norm. Its accuracy is ensured as long as the eigenvalues of the system matrix remain confined near the negative real axis, within the region of high accuracy of the rational approximation, which is for $r_{16,16}$ shown in the relative error contour plot in [5].

4. CRAM APPLICABILITY TO THE EXTENDED POINT KINETICS SYSTEM

In this section, the applicability of CRAM to the extended point kinetics system is assessed through an analysis of the spectral properties of the system matrix. As established earlier, the matrix is formed by augmenting the decay matrix with a first column that describes neutron irradiation of nuclides and a first row that represents neutron kinetics. To analyse the spectrum of the matrix, it is useful to represent it as a graph, in which each nuclide (and the neutron population) corresponds to a node, and each transmutation or decay is represented as a directed edge between nodes. In particular, a transmutation from nuclide i to j is represented as a directed edge from node j to node i . Once the matrix is interpreted as a directed graph, it can be decomposed into strongly connected components (SCCs), defined as maximal sets of nodes for which a path in each direction exists between every pair of nodes. This decomposition simplifies the spectral analysis, as the spectrum of the matrix is the union of the spectra of its SCCs [5].

Because no nuclide can decay back into any of its ancestors along a decay chain, the graph of a pure decay matrix is acyclic. Thus, in the case of the pure decay matrix, each nuclide forms a strongly connected component on its own (of size one), introducing an eigenvalue equal to its diagonal entry: zero for stable nuclides and the negative of the decay constant for unstable ones. When the first column and first row of the extended matrix are introduced, this structure changes fundamentally. The neutron irradiation column introduces directed edges from nuclides to the neutron population node, reflecting the dependence of nuclide concentration on neutron population. The delayed neutron production terms in the first row introduce directed edges from the neutron population to all delayed neutron precursors. Thus, a two-way dependency between the nuclides and the neutron population is introduced.

Delayed neutron precursors are produced either directly as fission products or through the decay chains of fission products, all of which originate from the fission of actinides. Consequently, the actinides, the precursors, the fission products upstream in their decay chains, and the neutron population together form one large strongly connected component. All remaining nuclides form SCCs of size one with the eigenvalues equal to the negatives of their decay constants. Thus, the applicability of CRAM to the extended point kinetics system can be evaluated by focusing solely on the spectral properties of the large strongly connected component.

For illustrative purposes, Figure 1 shows the large SCC of the extended point kinetics matrix corresponding to the CROCUS research reactor [9] using ENDF/B-VIII.0 library [10]. This SCC contains 343 nodes in total, of which 294 are delayed neutron precursors. An interesting feature is the appearance of the primordial U-238 decay chain in the right portion of the graph. This chain enters the SCC because it includes Tl-210, which is a delayed neutron precursor with an extremely small branching ratio for delayed neutron emission. In contrast, the JEFF-3.3 library [11] does not classify Tl-210 as a precursor, so this decay chain is absent from the SCC.

Figure 1. (a) Main strongly connected component of the extended point kinetics system for the CROCUS reactor (ENDF/B-VIII.0). (b) Graph representation of a 6-group point kinetics system.

For negative reactivity insertions, the evolution of the nuclides and the neutron population remains fully bounded in time, which results in a spectrum whose eigenvalues all have negative real parts. Under these conditions, CRAM can be safely used to approximate the matrix exponential. For positive reactivity insertions, the neutron population becomes unbounded in time. Eigenvalue decomposition of the large strongly connected component under positive reactivity insertions showed that there is only one eigenvalue with a positive real part, which is a positive real number, while all other eigenvalues have negative real parts. However, the applicability of CRAM is not fully dismissed in this case, because the region of high accuracy of the Chebyshev rational approximation extends into the domain of small positive values. This is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the relative error of the Chebyshev rational approximation in the IPF and PFD forms for the positive real values. As the approximation order increases, the high-accuracy region extends further and the transition to the low-accuracy region becomes steeper.

Since the matrix exponential is evaluated for $M\Delta t$, the timestep Δt can be selected as a scaling factor so that the largest eigenvalue of $M\Delta t$ is brought into the high-accuracy region of the approximation. This restriction on the timestep is also fully aligned with the quasi-static neutron irradiation assumption of the extended point kinetics system, which already requires smaller timesteps during large power variations to preserve its validity.

The positive eigenvalue of the large strongly connected component must be evaluated for different reactivity insertions in order to determine the timestep required to confine it within the high accuracy region of the Chebyshev rational approximation. The right plot in Figure 2 shows the corresponding largest eigenvalue for the extended and grouped point kinetics matrices as a function of the inserted reactivity, with examples provided for the CROCUS and MSFR reactors. For all positive reactivities, a strong consistency between the grouped and extended formulations is observed. Thus, the largest eigenvalue is equal to the inverse of the reactor period and corresponds to the largest real root of the inhour equation. For small positive reactivities, it is approximately $\rho\Lambda/(\Lambda + \sum \frac{\beta_i}{\lambda_i})$, while for prompt supercritical cases ($\rho > \beta_{\text{eff}}$) it approaches the prompt neutron generation term $(\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}})/\Lambda$. The maximum timestep required for an accurate solution can be directly inferred from the inserted reactivity and the kinetic parameters of the system, based on the limit on the maximum eigenvalue $\lambda_{\text{max}}\Delta t$ derived from the left plot in Figure 2. Selecting the largest timestep that preserves accuracy minimises the round-off errors accumulated during repeated applications of the approximation over long sequences of timesteps. Further analysis of this effect is provided in [2].

Figure 2. Left: Absolute relative error of the Chebyshev rational approximation in the PFD and IPF forms of different orders on the positive real axis. Right: Normalized maximum eigenvalue of the matrix spectrum for the extended and grouped point kinetics systems of the two reactors, CROCUS and MSFR.

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The accuracy of CRAM for the extended point kinetics system was assessed through a series of single-step calculations for timesteps ranging from 10^{-6} s to 10^2 s and for reactivity insertions between -2β and 2β . The test case corresponded to the extended point kinetics system of the CROCUS reactor using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library, with a system matrix of size 1814×1814 that includes 294 delayed neutron precursors. For each case, the computed neutron population was compared against a reference solution obtained using MATLAB's *expm* function (based on Padé approximation method) together with the Symbolic Math Toolbox at 50 digit precision. When evaluated with high precision arithmetic, the Padé approximation with scaling and squaring is no longer affected by the rounding errors that limit its accuracy in double precision. However, such high precision evaluations are extremely slow for matrices of this size: computing a single matrix exponential required more than a day of CPU time, making this approach impractical for routine calculations.

Figure 3 presents the absolute value of the relative errors for the neutron population for different reactivities and timesteps, obtained with CRAM in the IPF form of orders 16, 32, and 48. Black regions denote cases where the relative error exceeds 100%. As expected from the relative error curves in Figure 2, increasing the approximation order expands the high-accuracy region and leads to a much sharper transition toward the low-accuracy region. When the timestep is sufficiently small to confine the maximum real eigenvalue of $M\Delta t$ within the high accuracy region of the rational approximation, CRAM shows excellent accuracy for all tested reactivities, with relative errors on the order of double-precision.

It must be noted that the right choice of linear solver used within the CRAM algorithm to solve the systems of linear equations (Equation (8)) is crucial for obtaining an accurate solution. In this work, MATLAB's `mldivide` (backslash) operator was employed, which automatically selects an appropriate direct factorization based on the matrix properties and, for general sparse non-symmetric matrices, performs an LU factorization with partial pivoting. Iterative solvers have shown to exhibit inconsistent and unpredictable accuracy depending on the case, a behaviour that has also been observed previously in burnup calculations [12], and is primarily a consequence of the stiffness of the system matrix.

Figure 3. Relative error of CRAM solution for the neutron population in 10 base logarithmic representation, for different orders of approximation in the IPF form.

Although CRAM has previously been applied to classical point kinetics simulations [13], a systematic study on the mathematical conditions for its applicability has not been performed before. In addition to clarifying these conditions, the present work compares the performance of CRAM on the conventional point kinetics system with that of the ODE15s solver [14]. ODE15s is a variable-order, adaptive BDF method widely recommended for stiff systems and was selected for comparison based on its best performance in preliminary tests among MATLAB's stiff ODE solvers. The reference solution is again calculated with MATLAB's `expm` function and high precision arithmetic. The left part of Figure 4 presents the absolute value of the relative errors of ODE15s and CRAM of order 48 for the neutron population of the six-group point kinetics system over a range of reactivities and timesteps. Black regions indicate cases where the relative error exceeds 100%. As anticipated from Figure 2, CRAM provides relative errors of the order of double precision over a wide range of timesteps and reactivities, with a very sharp transition to cases where it can no longer be applied. On the other hand, ODE15s, despite employing adaptive time-stepping with automatic local error control, exhibits larger relative errors and a gradual loss of accuracy as the reactivity and timestep increase. The right part of Figure 4 shows the dominance of CRAM in CPU computation times over ODE15s. While CRAM exhibits very consistent performance, with computation times remaining below 1 ms for all tested cases, the computation time of ODE15s depends strongly on the rate of change of the solution vector and increases for larger reactivities and longer timesteps.

Figure 4. Accuracy and CPU time comparison between CRAM and ODE15s for the six-group point kinetics system.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work examined the applicability of the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) to the extended point kinetics system. The motivation for employing CRAM for calculating the matrix exponential stemmed from the large stiffness of the system matrix and its numerical similarity to the decay matrix, for which CRAM had already proven to be both accurate and fast, in contrast to conventional matrix exponential methods that are ill-conditioned under such conditions.

The graphical analysis of the matrix revealed the strongly connected component that dominates the critical spectral behaviour under positive reactivity insertions. Spectral analysis further showed that, for positive reactivities, this component introduces a single positive real eigenvalue whose magnitude closely follows the largest root of the inhour equation for the grouped formulation. Although CRAM is known to be accurate when applied to matrices whose eigenvalues lie near the negative real axis, the high-accuracy region of the Chebyshev rational approximation also extends slightly into the right half of the complex plane. Thus, if the timestep is chosen sufficiently small so that the eigenvalues of $M\Delta t$ remain within this region, CRAM can be safely applied to the extended point kinetics system, allowing the simultaneous modelling of power and nuclide evolution over different timescales and under various transient conditions.

The procedure for selecting an appropriate timestep was demonstrated, and numerical tests on the extended point kinetics system confirmed the validity of this approach. Moreover, CRAM was shown to outperform MATLAB's stiff ODE solver ODE15s in both accuracy and computational efficiency for the conventional point kinetics system.

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